

3. Smit Frederik, Driessen Geert & Felling Bert. *The functioning of the Platform for Ethnic Minority Parents in the Netherlands.*

The functioning of the Platform for Ethnic Minority Parents in the Netherlands

Frederik Smit, Geert Driessen & Bert Felling

ITS – Radboud University Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Abstract

In 2006, a beginning was made with the establishment of a national platform for ethnic minority parents and of local platforms for ethnic minority parents in thirty big cities in the Netherlands. The project is funded by the Ministry of Education, with the support of the national Dutch parents' associations. The goal is to stimulate parental involvement and participation. To reach the 'invisible' minority parents, the project employs the 'community-approach' paradigm. In addition, various innovative approaches are introduced to stimulate minority parents and their networks to participate in schools and to implement a culture aiming at change. The platforms develop debates about the policy of community-empowered schools in which the schools' pedagogical task is supported by other activities in the community.

1. Introduction

In the Netherlands, parents and teachers in primary education are increasingly expected to have meaningful and efficient interactions to make a combined effort in defining education and child-rearing (Driessen, Smit & Slegers, 2005). More and more, the relation between parents and school is characterized by cooperation and consultation.

Parents are seen as partners with whom one should cooperate. In the big cities more than half of the primary and secondary school students are non-western minorities (Driessen, 2008). The situation regarding the relation minority parents and schools is highly complicated. A large percentage of the minority parents have had little or no education and do not speak Dutch. This means that they have no insight in the Dutch education system and are hardly able to communicate with their children's teachers. At the same time the parents complain that they even have problems talking with their children, because the children increasingly only have a rudimentary understanding of their (parents') 'mother tongue'. As a consequence of these factors minority parents often do not know what is being taught at school. In addition, some of them, as part of their culture, feel that the educational sphere is not their responsibility, but solely that of the school. This does not mean, however, that they think education is not important. On the contrary, in general minority parents foster higher ambitions than native-Dutch parents do. Teachers, however, interpret the parents' absence and attitude negatively: in their opinion minority parents are not interested in their children's educational career and because of language problems they do not take the parents seriously. Which in turn has a negative effect on parents who are willing to participate in matters concerning school and education (Joshi, Eberly & Konzal, 2005).

2. Parental involvement and participation

2.1 Definitions of partnership, involvement and participation

Internationally, the notion of *partnership* is often used to refer to the significant cooperative relations between parents, schools and communities (Epstein et al., 2002). Partnership is construed as a process in which those involved aim to provide mutual support and attune their contributions to each other to the greatest extent

possible in order to promote the learning, motivation and development of pupils. The initiatives for a partnership must come from the school. Parents are generally interested, but often adopt a 'wait and see' attitude. The core elements in the development of a cooperative relationship between parents and school are: parental involvement and parental participation (Smit & Driessen, 2009).

In the literature, the notions of parental involvement and parental participation are often not clearly operationalized (Feuerstein, 2000). For purposes of the present study, the concept of *parental involvement* was defined as the role of the parents in the support of their own child, both at home (e.g., reading out loud) and at school (e.g., discussion of marks with teacher). The concept of *parental participation* was defined as active participation of parents in school activities.

2.2 Evidence for effects of parental involvement and participation

Despite the fact that the relevant research results were found to strongly diverge as a consequence of conceptual differences, many of the results point to a positive relation between the *involvement* of parents and the school development of their child (Ferguson, 2008; Nye, Turner & Schwartz, 2006). According to Desforges (2003), the most important factor is 'good parenting at home' with the following characteristics: the provision of a safe and stable environment, intellectual stimulation, the conduct of parent-child discussions, the functioning of parents as constructive role models who propagate the value of education and provide signs of high expectations for their children. The following elements are also of importance: the maintenance of contact with the school for the exchange of information, participation in school activities and the conduct of activities at the school and within the school administration. Carter (2003) points to the direct effects of parental involvement in addition to the more long-term effects. Desforges (2003) nevertheless suggests that parental involvement works primarily indirectly by shaping the self-image of the child as learner and fostering high expectations; parental involvement also stimulates certain attitudes, values and aspirations which can function as 'pro-social' and 'pro-learning' aspects. Still other authors find a reversed direction of causality for parental involvement and pupil achievement: Involvement only takes place when the performance of the child is judged to be insufficient by the parents or the school and it thus concerns a reaction to poor achievement or negative behavior on the part of the child. Smit (2005) points to the positive but modest effects of parental involvement on other outcome measures such as the well-being of the child. Empirical evidence regarding the relation between parental involvement and the affective functioning of pupils at school is scarce, however. Existing instruments used to map the affective functioning of pupils at school have yet to be related to the degree of parental involvement. Schools also tend to have fairly general and not very concrete objectives with regard to parental involvement. Furthermore, parental involvement does not have high priority in many schools and those policies actually in operation are not evaluated systematically. Involvement of parents in schools does not, thus, appear to be an objective in and of itself.

The offering of opportunities for parents to *participate* in the education of their children has been found to exert a positive influence on the cognitive development and achievement of pupils. However, a few studies show no effects of such opportunities (Mattingly et al., 2002). Parental participation is also often considered one of the most important components or characteristics of effective schools (Driessen, Smit & Slegers, 2005). In addition to the positive effects of parental participation on the school achievement of children, positive effects on the social functioning of pupils have also been found in various studies. This involves aspects of the behavior of pupils, their motivation, social competence, the relations between teachers and pupils, and the relations among the pupils themselves.

2.3 Variations in parental involvement and participation

Research on parental involvement has shown considerable variation to occur in the level of involvement and this variation to largely depend on the social-economic position and especially ethnic background of the parents (Bouakaz, 2007). Sheldon (2002) points to the importance of the size of the social networks of parents as an important predictor of parental involvement.

Research by Vogels (2002) has shown parental involvement in Dutch education to be an important theme although the involvement in primary education is much greater than that in secondary education. Vogels concludes that four groups of parents can be distinguished: partners, participants, delegators and invisible parents. The first two groups are closely involved in the child's school. Both partners and participants are actively involved in informal school-support activities. The group of partners is also active in the domain of formal participation, and this most active group consists of primarily parents with a high social-economic status (e.g., high level of education, high income). The largest group of participants consists of primarily parents with a middle to high social-economic position. The most important difference between the delegators and invisible parents is not so much the degree of active involvement, as both groups are relatively passive, but the backgrounds of the groups. The group of delegators involves primarily parents with a denominational philosophy of life and children attending an orthodox Protestant school. In the eyes of these parents, the directorate and teachers are the appointed experts and therefore the people responsible for the education of their children. This group of parents guards the foundations of the denominational school from a distance. The invisible group of parents consists of primarily parents with a low social-economic position. The parents in this group participate much less in various activities organized for pupils than the other groups. Differences also exist between Dutch parents and ethnic minority parents with respect to helping children with their homework, attendance of parent nights and talking about school within the family: Dutch parents undertake these forms of parental involvement relatively more often than ethnic-minority parents (Driessen, 2003; Smit, 2005).

2.4 The preparation of school staff and school boards

Epstein et al. (2002) have pointed out that the preparation of teachers to fulfill this task falls short. Teachers need new knowledge (e.g., insights regarding advantages and barriers) and new skills (e.g., involvement, participation) in order to interact more effectively with parents. School boards are weak agencies. Their rights and responsibilities are not clear. And they are unable to represent all parents and other stakeholders (Kristofferson, 2005). According to Johansson (2007) and Persson & Broman (2002), school staff and school boards should be equipped with new techniques, methods and skills related to communication and cooperation in order to expand parental participation and how school staff and parents can support cultural understanding, and cultural diversities in the school context.

3. Objectives of the research project

3.1 Research objective and research questions

The educational achievement and attainment of the minority children is on the rise, it is clear that they still lag considerably behind native-Dutch children. To improve their position, the Dutch Ministry of Education for a number of decades now has employed an educational priority policy (Driessen, 2008). Lately, the Ministry has pointed to parental involvement and participation as one of the main spearheads of this policy. In the wake of this decision a number of new initiatives were taken and funded.

In 2006, a beginning was made with the establishment of a national platform for ethnic minority parents and of local platforms for ethnic minority platforms in thirty big cities in the Netherlands. This project is funded by the Ministry of Education, with the support of the national Dutch parents' associations. The goal of

the platforms is to stimulate parental involvement and participation. To reach the ‘invisible’ minority parents, the project employs the ‘community-approach’ paradigm. In addition, various innovative approaches are introduced to stimulate minority parents and their networks to participate in schools and to implement a culture aiming at change.

The goal of the present evaluation study is to get a better understanding of the role of the national platform and the local platforms in stimulating minority parent participation at schools and in communities. More specifically, this study focuses on answering the following questions. What innovative policies of the national platform and the local platforms support schools success by creating partnerships with minority parents and communities? To what output have the efforts thus far, i.e. after three years, led? What are the outcomes of the efforts thus far? What recommendations can be given on the basis of this evaluation study?

3.2 Research methodology

The research involved a number of phases which built upon each other: (1) a preparatory review of the literature; (2) in-depth case studies of the national and the local platforms; (3) consultation with representatives of different relevant partners and organizations of parents; (4) analyses; (5) reporting.

The empirical part of the research focused on the national platform and a non-random selection of local platforms. Ten local platforms were selected that showed some continuity in terms of members and activities. A questionnaire with focused, structured and open-end items was presented to the chairpersons of the platforms, the management of schools that the platforms worked together with, and the authorities of the relevant cities.

For the analyses use was made of information from three sources, namely written material such as project plans, activities plans, quarterly and year reports, and notes of meetings; the project’s website and data base; and interviews with the various parties involved, such as members of the national platform and local platforms, the project team, the parent organizations, school board organizations and minority organizations.

The aim of the case studies was on the one hand, to gain in-depth insight into the strong and weak aspects of the project and the functioning of the different forms of cooperation between local platforms, schools and parents and the possible effects of the platforms’ approaches (*confirmatory, explanatory*). On the other hand, the intention was to identify good examples of the parent-school relationship for use by schools that wish to devote greater attention to optimizing this relationship as part of their policies, and to formulate recommendations with regard to developing and optimizing partnership between platforms and schools (*exploratory*) (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Yin, 2003).

The aim of the (interactive on-line) consultation with stakeholders was to solicit their views on the project, their understanding of the causes of possible problems and their perspectives on solutions (Krueger & Casey, 2000).

4. Results

4.1 The national platform

The national platform includes parents from various ethnic minority groups and representatives of national education and immigrant organizations.

The products that were developed (‘the output’) are: a vision document, (‘An approach of educational partnership’) and a quality mark of parental involvement (‘A measuring staff for a parent friendly school’).

The national platform employs a research-based approach: findings from various studies form the basis of policy priorities. In addition, the platform employs a dialogue strategy to stimulate the information exchange between the national platforms and the local platforms. Chair persons and active members of the

local platforms are encouraged to (also) become a member of the national platform and in such a way realize a better liaison between the national and local level.

The instruments developed pertain to the organizing of so-called Lower house debates and to communicating effectively with the school management. In addition manuals for conducting house visits and teacher training colleges are in progress.

4.2 The local platforms

In thirty big cities local platforms were set up. These platforms consist of volunteers that aim at improving the position of minority parents in schools. The establishment of the platforms proved to be an enormous endeavor. Members of the project team have recruited parents (i.e. volunteers) from various local networks. The project started at the beginning of 2006 and at the end of 2008 local platforms were active in thirty big cities. A basis was laid for partnership relations with education and welfare organizations, both at the national and local level.

The local platforms aim at being an intermediary between parents, schools and the local authorities. They organize thematic mornings at schools and debates on topics such as healthy nutrition, participation in the school council, special education, and testing at school.

The strategies and methods employed by the local platforms to realize their goals are the following (cf. Epstein et al., 2002; Koelen, Vaandrager & Colomer, 2001):

- *Connecting to the local situation*: the platform's approach connects as much as possible to the existing situation and specific needs of the minority parents in the municipalities. After gaps have been traced regarding the supply of activities new initiatives are set into motion building on existing expertise, facilities and networks.
- *Social network approach*: platforms try and gather information and then spread this via members of existing networks (e.g. immigrant organizations).
- *Intersectoral cooperation*: platforms try and stimulate the cooperation regarding planning and implementing between schools, teacher training colleges, municipalities and welfare organizations. In this way facets of problems of minority parents and children can be addressed at the same time and from multiple perspectives. The problems are addressed by giving lectures and presentations, by referring to specific institutions, and by consultation with other (volunteer) organizations. The extent to which platforms work together with other organizations varies, depending on the place and role that the members of the platform play in their network, the amount of time and energy that they want to spend on volunteer work and whether it is possible to use telephone, computer, etc. of the institution one works.
- *Environment strategy*: not only the individual immigrant parents, but also the social network of these parents (family, neighborhood) stand central in the approach. Attention is paid to creating an environment that allows for an increasing parent involvement.
- *Increasing involvement and participation*: stimulating a developmental process of which the core is to take minority parents serious and together with them create situations in such a way that they feel involved with school and the development of their children, to participate in the school organization, to be in a position to decide and to exert influence, to get a grip on the own situation and to have control over this situation.
- *Bottom-up strategy*: platforms work together with parents, principals and teaching staff of schools and other parties involved in the neighborhood focusing on what minority parents experience as a problem. What is important is that the supply of the institutions that participate (schools, municipality, welfare organizations) develop a demand-driven orientation towards parents.

The strategies employed especially have a chance of success when (cf. Epstein et al., 2002; Koelen, Vaandrager & Colomer, 2001; Rychetnik et al., 2002):

- Key persons in the municipality (politicians, civil servants, teachers, members of the parents' council) become a member of the local platform.
- Platforms have a clear vision on working together with schools and welfare organizations.
- Members of platforms possess adequate communicative competencies to engage in contact with municipalities, schools and welfare organizations and seduce them in working together.
- Members of platforms have enough knowledge and experience to provide made-to-measure advice and activities for the schools in need of help.

4.3 The project team

A project team assists the national platform and the local platforms in establishing the platforms and in setting up and implementing the various activities.

As of the end of 2007, the project team has stimulated the local platforms to reach minority parents via schools. The reason for this is that other approaches and instruments employed proved to lead to disappointing results. However, they were now confronted with a very defensive attitude of the school management and school teams regarding the contribution of minority volunteers to the optimization of the relationship minority parents and school (Smit & Driessen, 2009). This is the main reason why the stimulating of parental involvement and participation has not really come off the ground. Together with the national organization of school principals a pilot project was therefore started to try and solve these problems regarding difficult contacts with schools (cf. Epstein et al., 2002).

4.4 Differences between the traditional approach and the platform's approach

To reach minority parents and stimulate their involvement and participation, the project starts from an innovative paradigm that deviates from the traditional approach; see Table 1.

<<Table 1 about here >>

In the traditional approach of parental involvement and participation, where there is a clear division of responsibilities with respect to parents the school's staff can keep a formal distance to them. In a traditional and thematic approach the professionals set the agenda and systematically work on changing the parents' behavior. In the platform's approach, the members of the local platforms see the staff and parents as partners, who harmonize care at home and education at school, who keep each other well informed, who strive for collaboration and who both have a right to a substantial say in the educational process. All parties approach each other in an open fashion, they organize debates at local settings, they are not afraid of a 'sound' chaos, and they focus on each other's qualities in an idealistic tone (Smit, Driessen & Felling, 2009). The platform's approach stimulates the exchange of experiences, leads to new insights with regard to the quality of care and education at home and at school, provides parents and school staff with information as to how different cultures handle care and education in different settings. Parents, teaching staff, school management and school boards can profit from these experiences and insights.

4.5 Possible effects of the platform's approach

The main question is whether the functioning of the project team and the platforms has led to any effects with regard to improving the relation between parents and school. It appeared to be very difficult to establish a relationship between the approach and activities of the project team and platforms and possible output and outcomes because the interventions had not clearly been formulated at the start of the project. The project not only works with a top-down strategy but also with a bottom-up strategy and the design and implementation of change bear elements of a 'learning-while-doing' approach. The strategies of the project team have developed

during the course of the project depending on the changing circumstances and in consultation with the various stakeholders. From a strict evaluation perspective it is therefore quite impossible to establish effects and even more difficult to attribute them unambiguously to the interventions of the project team and the platforms (Koelen, Vaandrager & Colomer, 2001; Rychetnik et al., 2002).

Nevertheless, on the basis of the research findings we can establish that the local platforms mostly work enthusiastically to improve the visibility of minority parents and to give an impulse to the involvement with the educational career of their children. The local platforms in part come up to expectations to introduce a result-driven culture that aims at change at schools with regard to promoting and implementing involvement and participation of minority parents. The local platforms clearly steer in that direction.

The platform's approach in practice leads to many small successes and – for now – modest proven effects. Considering the learning process all parties involved find themselves in, it is desirable to learn of the experiences thus far. It is only in this way that the potential of this approach can be put to full use and that in time it can be determined how effective this approach really is (Rychetnik et al., 2002).

5. Conclusions

5.1 Strong and weak aspects of the project

A strong point of the project is the flexible way the members handle all kinds of unexpected and disappointing developments during the course of the project. The project meets a number of boundary conditions for a accommodating functioning: clear (written) agreements within the project team regarding the division of roles and tasks and decision-making processes, adequate leadership of the project management (control, supervision, enthusiasm), continuity of the project team (personal dedication, time to get to know each other, time and budget to develop and continue a collaboration process), a pleasant working atmosphere (open, constructive, respectful, desire to learn from one another) (Smit & Driessen, 2009).

A very weak point is that the platforms are totally depended of volunteers. It appeared that one cannot always build on them (attendance, keeping agreements, executing activities). Another point is that the project, being a new innovative 'organization', from time to time has to compete with the vested interests of well-established organizations, for instance parent organizations. In addition, the project has to fight the prejudice of schools and it takes quite some pains to gain the trust and convince schools that the platform has extra value (Bouakaz, 2007).

5.2 Recommendations

On the basis of these research findings the following approach with regard the optimalization of the project seems the most obvious. Regarding the *internal functioning* (Driessen et al., 2005; Smit, 2005): to organize the project in a tighter rein; to raise the professionalism of the members of the project team; to formulate the goals of the national platform SMART; to select the parents for the national platform and the local platforms more critically on the basis of a set of criteria; to train the members and to reward them adequately so as they will be able to develop activities independently and to work more aimed at change and results. Regarding the external functioning: (Epstein et al., 2002; Sheldon, 2002): the collaboration between the national parent organizations, the organization of school principals, school boards and local networks – such as immigrant organizations – should be implemented differently to better mobilize the willingness to change from schools and immigrant parents.

In developing and optimalization a true partnership between platforms and school teams it is of the utmost importance that platforms raise a number of fundamental issues and questions pertaining the interpretation and concretization of the concept of 'partnership' (Bouakaz, 2007; Johansson, 2007; Kohl,

Lengua & McMahon, 2000). What is our basis for the relation with the school team? What is our motivation to be engaged in schools? Do we as a platform have a positive basic attitude toward the school team? Is there a (growing) trust in each other? What is the joint importance? What can the school team and the platform expect from each other? How noncommittal are the contacts, the talks, and the collaboration? Is there a lower limit to the partnership, for both parties? How will the concept of partnership be given shape? How will we develop and maintain a good working relation with the school team? How can we aim at questions pertaining to the school's course with regard to parental involvement and participation? How will we pay attention to the process side of strengthening cultural understanding and policymaking with regard to parental involvement and participation, that is, with regard to the way the platform and the parents (in the parents' council and participation council) can be involved in the school's consultation and decision making? How can the platform become visible for (especially) minority parents and justify its added value?

References

- Bouakaz, L. (2007). *Parental involvement in school: What hinders and what promotes parental involvement in an urban school*. Malmö: Malmö Högskola.
- Carter, S. (2003). *The impact of parent/family involvement on student outcomes*. Eugene, OR: CADRE.
- Desforges, C. (2003). *The impact of parental involvement, parental support and family education on pupil achievements and adjustment*. London: DfES.
- Driessen, G. (2003). Family and child characteristics, child-rearing factors, and cognitive competence of young children. *Early Child Development and Care*, 173, (2/3), 323-339.
- Driessen (2008). *Towards citizenship education in the Netherlands*. Turin, It.: FIERI.
- Driessen, G., Smit, F., & Slegers, P. (2005). Parental involvement and educational achievement. *British Educational Research Journal*, 31, (4), 509-532.
- Epstein, J. Sanders, M., Simons, B., Salinas, K. Jansom, N., & Van Voorhis, F. (2002). *School, family and community partnerships*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press.
- Ferguson, C. (2008). *The school-family connection: Looking at the larger picture. A review of current literature*. Austin, TX: SEDL.
- Feuerstein, A. (2000). School characteristics and parent involvement: Influences on participation in children's schools. *Journal of Educational Research*, 94, (1), 29-39.
- Johansson, G. (2007). *Cultural diversities in education in the North. Research report*. Luleå: Luleå University of Technology.
- Joshi, A., Eberly, J., & Konzal, J. (2005). Dialogue across cultures: Teachers' perceptions about communication with diverse families. *Multicultural Education*, 13, (2), 11-15.
- Koelen, M., Vaandrager, L., & Colomer, C. (2001). Health promotion research: Dilemmas and challenges. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 55, 257-262.
- Kohl, G., Lengua, L., & McMahon, R. (2000). Parent involvement in school. Conceptualizing multiple dimensions and their relations with family and demographic risk factors. *Journal of School Psychology*, 38, (6), 501-523.
- Krueger, R., & Casey, M. (2000). *Focus groups. A practical guide for applied research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Kristoffersson M. (2005). *Local school boards with parents in majority - a new way for school development in Sweden?* Paper presented at the European Research Network About Parents in Education (ERNAPE), Oviedo, September 2005.
- Mattingly, D., Prinlin, R., McKenzie, T., Rodriguez, J., & Kayzar, B. (2002). Evaluating evaluations: The case of parent involvement programs. *Review of Educational Research*, 72, 549-576.

- Miles, M., & Huberman, A. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: an expanded sourcebook*, Thousand Oaks, Sage Publications.
- Nye, C., Turner, H., & Schwartz, J. (2006). *Approaches to parent involvement to improving the academic performance of elementary school age children*. Oslo: The Campbell Organization.
- Persson, S., & Broman, I. (2002). That's a quite different job. The delimitations of the teacher profession and the teacher's social education responsibility. *Journal of Swedish Educational Research*, 17, (4), 257-278.
- Rychetnik, L., Frommer, M., Hawe, P., & Shiell, A. (2002). Criteria for evaluating evidence on public health interventions. *Journal of Epidemiology and Community Health*, 56, 119-127.
- Sheldon, S. (2002). Parents' social networks and beliefs as predictors of parent involvement. *The Elementary School Journal*, 102, (4), 301-316.
- Smit, F. (2005). Ethnic minority parents and schools: Strategies to improve parental involvement and participation. In: M. Mendel (Ed.), *Schools' perspectives on collaboration with families and community* (pp. 99-114). Gdansk: University Gdansk.
- Smit, F., & Driessen, G. (2007). Parents and schools as partners in a multicultural, multireligious society. *Journal of Empirical Theology*, 20, (1), 1-20.
- Smit, F., & Driessen, G. (2009). Creating effective family-school partnerships in highly diverse contexts. Building partnership models and constructing parent typologies. In: R. Deslandes (Ed.), *International Perspectives on Contexts, Communities and Evaluated Innovative Practices Family-school-community partnerships*. Oxford: Routledge.
- Smit, F., Driessen, G., & Felling, B. (2009). *Innovaties in ouderbetrokkenheid en ouderparticipatie. Evaluatie project Platform Allochtone Ouders en Onderwijs*. Nijmegen: ITS.
- Vogels, R. (2002). *Ouders bij de les*. Den Haag: SCP.
- Yin, R. (2003). *Case study research, design and methods*. Newbury Park: Sage Publications.

Table 1 – Differences between the traditional approach and the approach of the platforms

	<i>Traditional approach</i>	<i>Platform approach</i>
<i>Concept of man</i>	Professionals with a noncommittal relationship with parents	Staff and parents as partners
<i>Methodology</i>	Inform, convince	Support, seduce, restrict
<i>Starting point</i>	The will of parents to change	The milieu of the people involved
<i>Themes</i>	Narrow: behavior	Broad: context of care and education; environment
<i>Approach</i>	Closed: thematic	Open: focused on what appeals to parents
<i>Agenda</i>	Education professional	'Lower house' debates with all parties involved
<i>Scale</i>	National, regional	Local setting
<i>Production</i>	Preprogrammed	Collaboration with all parties involved
<i>Type</i>	Systematic	'Sound' chaos
<i>Goal</i>	Adjusted behavior of parents ('re-educate')	Starting from the qualities of parents and provoke and stimulate them to employ these qualities
<i>Tone</i>	Realistic	Idealistic

ERNAPE 2009

*7th International Conference of the
European Research Network About Parents in Education*

DIVERSITY IN EDUCATION

Luleå University of Technology, Malmö University and Umeå University Sweden

Proceedings Edited by;

Gunilla Johansson and Margaretha Kristoffersson

ISBN siffrorna 978-91-86233-82-2